

THIAZOLIDONES. PART IV. SYNTHESIS OF 2-ARYL-3-BENZYL-4-THIAZOLIDONES

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Schiff's bases from aryl aldehydes and benzylamines have been condensed with thioglycolic acid to obtain 2-aryl-3-benzyl-4-thiazolidones.

2-Aryl-3-alkyl-4-thiazolidones exhibit anticonvulsant and anaesthetic properties (Troutman and Long, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 3436; Surrey, *ibid.*, 1949, 71, 3354; Chen *et al.*, *Arch. Neurol. Psychiat.*, 1951, 66, 329). In the light of anticonvulsant properties shown by *N*-benzyl- β -chloropropionamide (Kushner *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1951, 16, 1283), it was considered of interest to prepare 2:3-disubstituted thiazolidones having a benzyl group. With this end in view, several 2-aryl-3-substituted benzyl-4-thiazolidones have now been prepared by the condensation of Schiff's bases (not isolated) from aryl aldehydes and benzylamines with thioglycolic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Aryl-3-benzyl-4-thiazolidones were synthesised by the procedure adopted by Surrey *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 2911) with slight modifications.

A mixture of aldehyde (0.02 *M*) and benzylamine (0.02 *M*) in dry benzene (25 c.c.) was refluxed with a Dean and Stark water separator. After the theoretical quantity of water had separated (4-5 hours), thioglycolic acid (2.0 g.) was added and refluxing was continued till water had ceased to separate.

Thiazolidones from benzaldehyde and substituted benzylamines separated directly from benzene solution. In other cases, the residue, after removal of benzene, was taken up in ether, washed successively with sodium bicarbonate solution, dilute HCl (1:1) and 10% sodium bisulphite solution to remove respectively any acid formed during the reaction, benzylamine and aldehyde, remaining unchanged. It was finally washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent evaporated. The oily residue deposited crystals on long standing (in some cases a month).

Thiazolidones (yields about 60%) were crystallised from ethanol. Compounds are listed in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	R = .	R' = .	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.	
					Found.	Calc.
1.	H	H	153-54°	(Troutman & Long, <i>loc. cit.</i>)		
2.	H	<i>o</i> -Cl	122°	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ONClS	10.7	10.5
3.	H	<i>p</i> -Cl	154°	"	10.4	"
4.	H	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	98°	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ ONS	11.1	11.3
5.	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	130°	"	11.4	"
6.	H	3:4-DiMe	126°	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ ONS	10.9	10.8
7.	H	2:4-DiMe	156°	"	11.0	"
8.	H	2:5-DiMe	82°	"	10.6	"
9.	H	<i>p</i> -Br	147°	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ONBrS	9.0	9.2
10.	H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	138°	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₂ NS	10.9	10.7
11.	<i>o</i> -Cl	H	75°	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ONClS	10.4	10.5
12.	<i>o</i> -Cl	<i>o</i> -Cl	110°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ONCl ₂ S	9.7	9.5
13.	<i>o</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -Br	103°	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ONClBrS	8.5	8.4
14.	<i>p</i> -Cl	H	73°	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ONClS	10.4	10.5
15.	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	115°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ONClS	10.0	10.1
16.	<i>o</i> -OH	H	150°	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₂ NS	11.1	11.2
17.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	H	62°	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₂ NS	10.6	10.7
18.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	3:4-DiMe	86°	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ O ₂ NS	9.6	9.8
19.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	2:4-DiMe	112°	"	10.0	"
20.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	<i>p</i> -Br	119°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ NBrS	8.7	8.5

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